

Iron-free Aluminum Sulphate from Bauxite

SHIVA PRASAD* and LAÉRCIO G. DE OLIVEIRA

Chemical Engineering Department, Centre for Sciences and Technology, Universidade Federal da Paraíba, 58109-970 Campina Grande, PB, Brazil

Manuscript received 19 July 1995, revised 27 February 1996, accepted 24 June 1996

A method for leaching aluminum sulphate from low-grade bauxite and extracting iron from the leach solution has been studied. It was found that a 200 mesh bauxite sample mixed with a stoichiometric amount of 30% sulphuric acid solution requires 2 h for complete conversion at 95° and 330 rpm stirring. An aqueous solution of this impure aluminum sulphate (Fe₂O₃, 2.6%) may crystallise into an acceptable quality of the product when treated with ethanol under suitable control of concentration, temperature and cooling rate. Further removal of the iron contents has been done by liquid-liquid extraction using di-2-ethylhexylphosphoric acid diluted in toluene. The final product has been found to contain less than 0.01% iron.

Aluminum occurs widely in nature in silicates such as clays and feldspars, as hydrated oxide (bauxite) and as cryolite. The potential-pH diagram¹ suggests that the metal can be leached by chemical dissolution in either acidic or alkaline media,

Both the reactions have been used in the extraction of aluminum. Sulphuric acid pressure leaching of low-grade bauxites and laterites has been utilised². Low-grade bauxite and clay are more amenable to acid extraction than to alkaline treatment, but the aluminum salts resulting from an acid leach are always contaminated with, and therefore difficult to separate from iron salts. Any acid process for the production of alumina is thus confronted with the problem of first separating the iron and aluminum salts formed during extraction of the ore. When sulphuric acid is used the resulting salts are sulphates, therefore, an effective purification procedure will provide a source of iron-free alum independent of the Bayer process.

The fact that aluminum sulphate can be precipitated from its aqueous solution by addition of ethanol has long been recognised, and the marked solubility of ferric sulphate in this same organic solvent is well established. Vitorf³ was apparently the first to propose the application of this phenomenon as a practical method for the purification of crude alum solutions. Roller⁴ conducted considerable experimentation on the fundamental considerations of the problem. Cell-grade alumina should not contain more than 0.01% iron, but it has been difficult to remove iron from aluminum leach solution in a corresponding level. The development of solvent-extraction technology has provided a new avenue for iron removal from acid leach solutions at a reasonable cost⁵. Fisher and coworkers⁶ were the first to suggest the liquid-liquid extraction technique, which is now used extensively for large-scale separation of lanthanides.

The extractants used are either phosphorus-based or

long-chain organic amines^{5,7}. Phosphorus-based organic compounds have been reported to provide the greatest efficiency in solvent-extraction separations. Tri-n-butylphosphate (TBP), the most thoroughly investigated extractant is used with about 15 M nitric acid that is essential to its efficient use. The reagent can be used undiluted as the organic phase⁸ or diluted with some hydrocarbon as the organic phase⁹. The extractant di-2-ethylhexylphosphoric acid (HDEHP) has a low solubility in water and an enhanced stability over TBP toward acid-induced hydrolysis, and is better choice for separation¹⁰. HDEHP is used extensively for large-scale separations of rare-earth elements. The average separation factor for adjacent Ln³⁺ ion¹¹ is ca. 2.5. The problem of separation of iron impurities from alum should be much less complicated than the separation of lanthanides. Aluminum being non-transition element does not have tendency to form chelated complex with the phosphate-based extractants and should prefer to stay in aqueous phase, whereas iron, a transition element, should go to the organic phase. Based on this hypotheses, investigations on the use of phosphate based organic extractant (HDEHP) for removal of iron from alum were initiated.

Results and Discussion

The bauxite used in this study was found to have an average composition (wt.%): Al₂O₃ 53.0, Fe₂O₃ 12.5, SiO₂ 5.5, TiO₂ 1.0 and loss on ignition 28.0. It was a red coloured low quality bauxite due to high iron content.

Determination of leaching conditions: To study the effect of variation of acid concentration on the leaching process, bauxite (56 g) was treated for 2 h with conc. H₂SO₄ (45 ml) in volumetric concentration range of 15–35%. Fig. 1, curve 1, demonstrates that the leaching of aluminum increases with increase in concentration of the acid and reaches to the extent of complete extraction with 30% H₂SO₄. Besides this, it was observed that at higher concentration (35%) of the acid the physical characteristics of the leach product affected the velocity of sedimentation and filtration due to paste-type solidification of

tetradecahydrate of alum¹² on cooling. Similar behaviour was observed by Schultze and coworkers⁵ during acid-leaching of caulinitic clay. For rest of the leaching studies a 30% concentration of H₂SO₄ was chosen.

Fig. 1. Acid leaching of bauxite at 95° and 330 rpm agitation: (1) effect of the acid concentration on leaching (time 2 h, vol. of conc. H₂SO₄ 45 ml), (2) effect of quantity of acid on leaching (time 2 h, concentration of acid 30%) and (3) effect of time on leaching (45 ml of concentrated acid diluted to 30%).

Fig. 1, curve 2, shows that the conversion of alumina increases linearly with increase in quantity of sulphuric acid till at the point where the volume of the concentrated acid reaches to 40 ml. after which the leaching rate decreases. With 45 ml of the concentrated acid almost all the alumina (99.3%) present in the bauxite sample got leached. Fig. 1, curve 3, demonstrates that the time needed for completion of the reaction of the bauxite sample with 45 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ diluted to 30% (v/v) is 2 h. A 88% of the conversion was completed during the first 1 h. It was noted that almost all iron present in the bauxite was leached during the first hour of the treatment, and any increase in hold-time resulted in a slight decrease in iron percentage.

Purification of the leached alum with ethanol: The impure aluminum sulphate obtained from the leaching step contains ferrous and ferric sulphates as the principal impurities. It is well-known that aluminum sulphate can be precipitated from its aqueous solution by addition of ethanol whereas iron sulphate remains in solution. To explore its applicability on purification of alum, investigations on relative solubilities of ferric, ferrous and aluminum sulphates in ethanol-water system were carried out. The results (Fig. 2) show that ferric sulphate is about 100 times more soluble than aluminum sulphate in aqueous ethanolic system. The solubility of alum is very low when ethanol concentration is >55% and goes to a minimum level at 80% ethanol (curve 3).

To optimise the purification process of impure aluminum sulphate, the effect of variation of concentration

Fig. 2. Solubility of ferric, ferrous and aluminum sulphates in ethanol-water solutions at 25° in presence of 1% H₂SO₄: (1) Al₂(SO₄)₃, (2) FeSO₄ and (3) Fe₂(SO₄)₃.

of ethanol and of the treatment temperature were investigated. Fig. 3, curve 1, demonstrates the results of iron extraction on addition of different volumes of ethanol to hot (92°) aqueous solution of aluminum sulphate. It shows that 70% ethanol is most effective in removing iron. Further, it was noted that slow cooling rate gave better results. Thermal studies on cooling rate showed that crystallisation of aluminum sulphate is an exothermic process and the crystal formation starts at 59.8°. The crystals were found to be of hexadecahydrate aluminum sulphate. The effect of variation of temperature on iron extraction was studied with 70% ethanol. The results show (Fig 3, curve 2) that the increase in temperature favours the extraction of iron. At low

Fig. 3. (1) Effect of variation of ethanol concentration on extraction of iron from impure alum and (2) effect of variation of temperature on extraction of iron with 70% ethanol.

temperatures (25°) the process was unsuccessful due to formation of emulsion. Ethanol used in the extraction can be regenerated by distillation for recycling in the purification process¹³.

Extraction of remaining iron with HDEHP : The aluminum sulphate obtained after alcoholic crystallisation was further purified by liquid-liquid extraction process using organophosphoric acid (HDEHP) diluted with toluene as organic extractant.

An aluminum sulphate solution (3.4 ppm Fe₂O₃) at pH 2.97 was contacted with an equal volume of the organic phase at 25°. Fig. 4 shows that the percentage of iron extracted by the organic phase increases with increase in concentration of HDEHP. Similar observation for extraction of rare earth elements was reported by Blake and coworkers¹⁴. The distribution coefficient was found to increase from 5.4 to 14.5 with an increase of HDEHP concentration from 10⁻³ to 10⁻² M in the organic phase.

Fig. 4. Extraction of iron vs [HDEHP]

The experiments with different concentrations of the extractant showed that, under the experimental conditions, a concentration of 0.001 M HDEHP is not enough for extraction of iron >2.5 ppm (Fig. 5, curve 1). For such samples a concentration of 0.01 M HDEHP and the aqueous phase pH 2.5 were found to be suitable (Fig. 5, curve 2).

Fig. 5. Effect of [HDEHP] on extraction of iron : (1) 10⁻³ M and (2) 10⁻² M HDEHP

Multistage experiments showed that as the iron content in aqueous phase falls after each stage, the distribution coefficient and efficiency of the next stage goes on decreasing. The extractant HDEHP exists as a dimer¹⁵ in the organic phase, and extraction data are found to agree with the equilibria,

It is believed that a chelated structure of the type,

exists in the organic phase, although the exact nature of the extracted species depends upon the ratio of the reactants in the extraction process. In accordance with this mechanism, the extraction of iron was found to be described by an inverse third-power dependence upon the hydrogen ion concentration. Therefore, the iron-loaded organic extractant can be regenerated by contacting with an aqueous solution of sulphuric acid at a suitable concentration⁵. Higher concentration of acid will take the iron-extraction equilibrium to the left, thus favouring the iron to move to the acidic aqueous phase. Aluminum being a non-transition element does not have tendency to form such chelate complex with the organic extractant and therefore remains in the aqueous phase.

The results presented here show that the 200 mesh bauxite sample mixed with 30% H₂SO₄ in stoichiometric ratio, at 95° and at a stirring rate of 330 rpm requires 2 h for complete leaching. The impure aluminum sulphate (1.7% Fe) obtained from the acid leach can be purified to the level of 0.14% Fe by crystallising with ethanol under suitable conditions. However, alum with lesser iron impurity will give a higher purity final product¹⁶. The remaining iron content can be eliminated by the extractant HDEHP (10⁻² M) diluted with toluene. The distribution coefficient (*D*) increases with increase in iron concentration in the original solution, e.g. *D* is 16.1 for 3.5 ppm Fe₂O₃ and 19.9 for 10.0 ppm. Further work is being carried out for elimination of other impurities, if any, present in the product.

Experimental

Sulphuric acid, ethanol, toluene, ferrous ammonium sulphate and potassium thiocyanate (G.R., Merck) and di-2-ethylhexylphosphoric acid (Sigma) were used. The bauxite sample was obtained from Rio Trombetas region (Brazil).

Bauxite leaching was performed in a bench-scale double-walled glass flask (600 ml capacity; 3-necks, 12 cm length, 8 cm diameter) equipped with a mechanical stirrer (Fisaton 713T) and a reflux condenser. The temperature

was maintained by thermostat which passed hot water flux through the double-wall space. Solvent extraction experiments were conducted in separatory funnels to determine data points for equilibrium diagrams and to measure the effects of individual variables. A Metronic EF1 spectrophotometer was used.

The experimental part consisted of three steps : leaching of bauxite, extraction of iron from the leach by ethanol, and further purification of the alum by liquid-liquid extraction with HDEHP.

Leaching : The bauxite was crushed and ground to pass through 200 mesh sieve. Leaching was conducted in the 3-necked double-walled glass flask. The bauxite sample (56 g) was added slowly to sulphuric acid of required concentration in the reaction flask. The system was maintained at 95° and at a constant agitation of 330 rpm. A series of leaching experiments was performed to study the reaction parameters : stoichiometry, concentration of the acid, and time of the reaction. At the end of each batch a heterogeneous product containing aluminum sulphate and co-leached iron sulphate in solution and silicates and other insoluble impurities in the form of solid were obtained. A commercial glue (cola tenaz) (0.5 ml) was added as flocculating agent and then solids were separated under vacuum-filtration. The filtrate was evaporated to about 100 ml, cooled to form crystals and then dried in a desiccator for 48 h. The aluminum sulphate obtained was analysed for iron and aluminum. Iron was determined spectrophotometrically by thiocyanate method and aluminum by difference after precipitation as hydroxide¹⁷.

Extraction of iron by ethanol : The impure aluminum sulphate obtained from the leaching step was purified by ethanol³. The experiments were conducted in the same equipment as used for leaching of the mineral. To aluminum sulphate (10 g) dissolved in a minimum quantity of water, were added conc. H₂SO₄ (2 ml) and H₂O₂ (10 ml) to avoid hydrolysis and to oxidise ferrous to ferric, respectively. Effect of variation of ethanol concentration was studied by adding different volumes of the alcohol at room temperature to the alum solution at 92°. Effect of variation of temperature on extraction of iron was investigated at 70% concentration of ethanol. The system was stirred at 330 rpm for 20 min and then kept undisturbed for 4 h. The crystallised aluminum sulphate was then filtered and dried for 48 h in an oven at 50°. The product was analysed for iron and aluminum as in the leaching step. The aluminum sulphate was found to be in the state of hexadecahydrate.

Purification of aluminum sulphate by HDEHP : The aluminum sulphate was further purified by liquid-liquid ex-

traction method using different concentrations of HDEHP in toluene. An aqueous solution of aluminum sulphate was maintained in direct contact with the organic phase for 5 min. A series of experiments was performed to study the effect of concentration of iron in the aqueous phase, concentration of HDEHP in the organic phase, and number of stages on efficiency of purification of the alum. The pH values of the aqueous solution were also noted before and after the extraction stages.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to the CNPq, Brasilia, for the financial help and to kepter B. Franca for useful discussion on liquid-liquid extraction and for arranging HDEHP sample from Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Canterbury, Kent, U.K.

References

1. M. POURBAIX, "Atlas of Electrochemical Equilibria in Aqueous Solution", Pergamon, New York, 1966.
2. T. R. SCOTT, *J. Met.*, 1962, 14, 121.
3. N. VITTORE, *Trans. Inst. Econ. Mineral. Petrog. (USSR)*, 1924, 8, 1.
4. P. S. ROLLER, U.S. Pat. 2 303 668/1946.
5. L. E. SCHULTZE, J. A. EISELE, M. T. MORIMOTO and D. J. BAUER, *U.S. Bur. Mines, Rept. Invest.*, 1979, 8353.
6. W. FISCHER, W. DIETZ and O. JUBERMANN, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1937, 25, 348.
7. D. F. PEPPARD in "Progress in the Science and Technology of the Rare Earths", ed. L. EYRING, Pergamon, New York, 1964, Vol. 1, pp. 89-109; B. WEAVER in "Progress in the Science and Technology of the Rare Earths", ed. L. EYRING, Pergamon, New York, 1964, Vol. 1, p. 85-88; 1968, Vol. 3, pp.129-148; T. K. KIM and M. B. MACINNIS, *Metall. Soc. AIME*, 1981, 33; J. D. ROCHA, Masters Dissertation, UFPB, Campina Grande, PB, Brazil, 1985; J. F. GOLDENBERG and C. ABBRUZESE, *Int. J. Min. Processing*, 1983, 10, 241.
8. D. F. PEPPARD, J. P. FARIS, P. R. GRAY and G. W. MANSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 57, 294.
9. D. F. PEPPARD, W. J. DRISCOLL, R. J. SIRONEN and S. McCARTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1957, 4, 326; E. HESFORD, E. E. JACKSON and H. A. C. MACKAY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 9, 279.
10. D. F. PEPPARD, G. W. MASON, J. L. MAIER and W. J. DRISCOLL *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1957, 4, 334.
11. W. L. SILVERNAIL and N. J. GOETZINGER in "Kirk-Othmer's Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", ed A. STANDEN, 2nd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1968, Vo. 17, pp. 143-168.
12. H. LEITCH, H. G. IVERSON and J. H. CLEMMER, *Bur. Mines, Rept. Invest.*, 1966, 6744.
13. E. A. GEE and W. K. CUNNINGHAM, *U.S. Bur. Mines, Rept. Invest.*, 1948, 4191.
14. C. A. BLAKE, JR., C. F. BAES, JR., K. F. BROWN, C. F. COLEMAN and J. C. WHITE, 'Second United Nations Intl. Conf. on the Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy', USA, 1958.
15. S. M. DESHPANDE, N. P. K. KRISHNAN and T. K. S. MURTHY, 'Solvent Extraction of Metals Symposium', Bombay, 1979, p. V-6.1.
16. S. PRASAD, K. B. FRANCA and R. P. BRITO, *Reun. An. SBPC*, 1989, 41, 44.
17. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1968.